

FOR DUPUYTREN'S CONTRACTURE DISEASE SPECIAL USE SPLINT

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Annotation: This article contains the worldwide prevalence of orthopedic diseases, Dupuytren's contracture, and recommendations for its treatment. Disadvantages of general splints used for Dupuytren's contracture and the advantages of the special splint we recommend are discussed.

Key words: Dupuytren's contracture, bending, dynamic, palm, patient, finger.

It is known that in today's advanced medicine, the main focus is on the treatment of the disease in a short time without complications, creating comfort for the patient. The following conclusions were drawn after statistical analysis of common diseases in the world.

After following the systematic review processes, 86 studies were selected for meta-analysis. The sample size of the study was 103,334,579 people in the age range of 15–105 years. Using meta-analysis, the prevalence of osteoporosis in the world was reported to be 18.3. While the prevalence of osteoporosis among men of the world was found to be 11.7[1]. Statistics show that orthopedic diseases are among the most common diseases in the world. Our article is also about the common orthopedic disease Dupuytren's contracture and the special that we want to produce for it.

Dupuytren's disease first appears in the written medical records in Basel, Switzerland in 1614 when doctor Felix Platter examined a stonemason whose left ring finger and little finger were contracted into his palm[2]. By evaluating 85 studies (10 in Asia, 56 in Europe, 2 in Africa and 17 studies in America) with a total sample size of 6628506 individuals, the prevalence of Dupuytren disease in the world is found as 8.2% According to the subgroup analysis, in terms of underlying diseases, the highest prevalence was obtained in patients with type 1 diabetes with 34.1% The results of meta-regression revealed a decreasing trend in the prevalence of Dupuytren disease by increasing the sample size and the research year ($P < 0.05$) [3]. Dupuytren's Disease Dupuytren's disease is a condition that affects the fascia—the fibrous layer of tissue that lies underneath the skin in the palm and fingers. In patients with Dupuytren's, the fascia thickens, then tightens over time. This causes the fingers to be pulled inward, towards the palm, resulting in what is known as a "Dupuytren's contracture."

In some patients, a worsening Dupuytren's contracture can interfere with hand function, making it difficult for them to perform their daily activities. Description

the fascia is a layer of tissue that helps to anchor and stabilize the skin on the palm side of the hand. Without the fascia, the skin on your palm would be as loose and moveable as the skin on the back of your hand. In patients with Dupuytren's disease, this palmar fascia slowly begins to thicken, then tighten.

Often, Dupuytren's is first detected when lumps of tissue, or nodules, form under the skin in the palm. This may be followed by pitting on the surface of the palm as the diseased tissue pulls on the overlying skin.

The cause of Dupuytren's disease is not completely known, but most evidence points towards genetics as having the most important role.

There are anecdotal reports of Dupuytren's emerging or worsening after a patient experiences an injury or an open wound (including surgery) to his or her hand; however, there is no good evidence to support this. There is also no compelling evidence to suggest that it is caused by overuse of the hand.

Risk Factors

There are a number of factors that are believed to contribute to the development or worsening of Dupuytren's disease. These include:

- Gender. Men are more likely to develop the condition than women.
 - Ancestry. People of northern European (English, Irish, Scottish, French, and Dutch) and Scandinavian (Swedish, Norwegian, and Finnish) ancestry are more likely to develop the condition.
 - Heredity. Dupuytren's often runs in families.
 - Alcohol use. Drinking alcohol may be associated with Dupuytren's.
 - Certain medical conditions. People with diabetes and seizure disorders are more likely to have Dupuytren's.
 - Age. The incidence of the condition increases with age.
- Currently, there is no cure for Dupuytren's; however, the condition is not dangerous.
 - Although it varies from patient to patient, Dupuytren's usually progresses very slowly and may not become troublesome for many years. In fact, for some patients, the condition may never progress beyond developing lumps in the palm.

Nonsurgical Treatment

- **Steroid injection.** Corticosteroids are powerful anti-inflammatory medications that can be injected into a painful nodule. In some cases, a corticosteroid injection may slow the progression of a contracture. The effectiveness of a steroid injection varies from patient to patient.
- **Splinting.** Splinting *is not known to prevent* the progression of a finger contracture. Forceful stretching of the contracted finger may not be helpful and, in fact, could cause an injury to the finger or hand.

Splinting may be used after surgery for Dupuytren's contracture to protect the surgical site; however, it is not known if it reduces the risk of recurrent contracture or tightening of the healing wound.

Surgical Treatment

If the contracture interferes with hand function, your doctor may recommend surgical treatment. The goal of surgery is to reduce the contracture and improve motion in the affected fingers.

There is no known cure for Dupuytren's contracture; however, surgery is intended to "set back the clock" by reducing the restricting effect of the cords by either disrupting or removing them. Unfortunately, the healing tissues will form with the same potential to develop cords in the future—but the gains in hand function can still be substantial.

The surgical procedures most commonly performed for Dupuytren's contracture are:

- Fasciotomy
- Subtotal palmar fasciectomy

- Recovery. Severe problems are not common after surgery, but you should expect some pain, swelling, and stiffness. Although the goal of surgery is to improve digital straightening, sometimes patients can lose flexion of the involved digits due to stiffness. Elevating your hand above your heart and gently moving your fingers will help decrease swelling and should improve stiffness.
- Physical therapy can help improve strength and function in your fingers and hand, reduce swelling, and aid in wound care. Often, a hand therapist will make a splint for you to wear during recovery.
- Outcomes. Most patients have improved movement in their fingers after surgery. However, because the condition is not "cured" with surgery, about 20 percent of patients will experience a meaningful degree of contracture recurrence. Additional surgery may be required for some patients[4].

As we mentioned above, 2 different methods are proposed for the treatment of this disease. Splints are widely used for both methods. What are good tires used for? If the patient does not choose surgery, special splints are needed to ensure the movement of the patient's fingers. Or in patients who have chosen surgery, splints are also necessary to reduce swelling after surgery, to provide movement of the fingers. Are there such tires in our country? Unfortunately no. In most cases, doctors who treat this disease use general splints, but this has some disadvantages, in particular, it limits the movement of the patient's healthy fingers, that is, since the splint is designed for all fingers, the healthy fingers also remain under the splint or their dynamics are limited, as a result, the patient cannot move freely with his hands.

Secondly, it is known that the bending angle of the fingers is different in different stages of the disease. Bending of the fingers in the early stages of the disease is different from the bending in the advanced stage of the disease. Common splints are not adapted for this. That is, it does not depend on the stage of the disease. Is used in general for all. Another reason is that it is not aesthetically pleasing. If the patient is in a commonly used splint, the patient will feel ashamed of himself due to the rough structure of the splint, and the patient cannot hide his hands in his pockets to protect them from cold or heat. And we want to offer you special

splint for this disease, here is the general view of the model.

Another advantage is that the price of this splint is not expensive and patients can easily buy it. Since it is possible to control the degree of bending, this splint can be used many times. Normal splints do not have this

option, so they should be replaced from time to time. This requires time and money.

In conclusion, this splint has many advantages, in particular:

- it does not spare the movement of healthy fingers;

- it saves money and time;
- it gives chance bending without difficulties;
- due to the possibility of controlling the degree of bending it is aesthetically beautiful and very comfortable for the patient.

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